

Step 1: Get un-expanded template network

Get all possible metabolic reactions

www.genome.jp/pathway/map01100

How do we fill the network?

Each reaction requires 2 things to be expanded:

- The starting substrates must be available (i.e. produced by a member of the holobiont)
- There is at least 1 available KO # encoding the given step

Step 2: Host Expansion

Using ALL of the host's capabilities (i.e., any compound/reaction found in their metabolic network), we begin to fill in the template network

Aphid genome (api)

Step 3: Obligate Expansion

Aphid genome (api) + *Buchnera 5A*

Using ALL of the obligate(*Buchnera*) symbiont's KO #s (NOT their compounds),

We perform sequential expansion rounds.

(i.e., find all reactions now satisfied by the obligate symbionts genes, add them to the network – keep going until nothing new can be added)

Step 3: Obligate Expansion

Note – this will **not** use up all of the obligate symbiont's genes – only the ones that are satisfied by the host environment (the compounds it provides)

Green are the KO #s that were not expanded, because their substrates weren't satisfied by the host environment...these would be candidates for further study (e.g. support directly by compounds from the diet that do not first require transformation by hosts)

Step 3: Facultative Expansion

Same process as the
Obligate expansion

This time, though, the KOs
being turned on could either
be from the Facultative
symbiont itself OR because
it allows more of the
obligate KOs to turn on

Aphid genome (api) + *Buchnera 5A* + *Fukatsuia*

Step 3: Facultative Expansion 2

If there are 2 facultative symbionts in the focal community (vs. singly infected communities, vs. just host + *Buchnera* vs. just host), we combine their KO #s and treat them as one cycle for further expansion

Aphid genome (api) + *Buchnera 5A* + *Fukatsuia* + *Hamiltonella A*

